

Working Paper

The EU Economic
Constitution After Covid-19
and “Next Generation EU”

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Abstract

The paper examines from a legal perspective the economic policy measures adopted by the institutions of the European Union (EU) to respond to the Covid-19 pandemic, and explores their implications for the constitutional architecture of Economic & Monetary Union (EMU). The article maps the complex set of instruments quickly put in place by EU supranational and intergovernmental institutions since the outburst of the health crisis and focuses on the “Next Generation EU” (NGEU) Recovery Plan proposed in 2020 and rendered operational since 2021. The article examines the consequences of the economic policy measures adopted in response to Covid-19 on the functioning of Europe’s EMU, and argues that NGEU plays a major role in rebalancing EMU and endowing it with a fiscal capacity. As such, the article contrasts the responses to Covid-19 to those the EU had taken to address the euro-crisis and reflects on the long term consequences for the future of the EU.

Keywords: Covid-19, Economic and Monetary Union, European Union, Fiscal Capacity, Next Generation EU

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I. INTRODUCTION

The outburst of Covid-19 has profoundly challenged and changed the world we live in. As the former President of the European Central Bank (ECB) Mario Draghi put it, Covid-19 immediately appeared to be ‘a human tragedy of potentially biblical proportions’.¹ Since the explosion of the pandemic in spring 2020, the institutions and member states of the European Union (EU) have taken unprecedented steps to tackle this dramatic health crisis and its devastating socio-economic consequences. The quick spread of the virus starting in late February 2020 forced governments and public authorities world-wide to adopt unprecedented measures, including lockdowns, border closures and requisition of essential properties to contain contagions and prevent hospitalizations and deaths. At the same time, if public authorities in the early days of the pandemic focused on the adoption of sanitary measures to address the dramatic health costs of Covid-19, they quickly had to shift attention on the devastating socio-economic implications of the pandemic.

The purpose of this chapter is to outline from an EU law and policy perspective the key economic policy responses adopted by the EU to address the Covid-19 pandemic and to assess their implications on Europe’s Economic and Monetary union (EMU).² As such, this chapter focuses specifically on the economic-related aspects of the response to the pandemic, with the aim to assess their impact on the European architecture of economic governance. As is well known, EMU represents a pillar of the EU and is one of the most tangible achievements of European integration. Nevertheless, the constitutional architecture of EMU has been afflicted since its creation by a significant imbalance between the monetary policy, which was centralized in a new federal

¹ M Draghi, ‘Interview ‘We Face a War Against Coronavirus and Must Mobilize Accordingly’’ (25 March 2020) *Financial Times*, www.ft.com/content/c6d2de3a-6ec5-11ea-89df-41bea055720b.

² This chapter builds on F Fabbrini, ‘The Legal Architecture of the Economic Responses to COVID-19’ (2021) 59 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 186; and F Fabbrini, ‘Europe’s Economic & Monetary Union beyond Covid-19’, report commissioned by the Presidency of the Eurogroup / Department of Finance of Ireland, June 2021.

institution – the ECB – and the economic policy, which instead remained decentralized at state level. In fact, while EMU was transformed significantly in the aftermath of the euro-crisis, the legal and institutional reforms adopted in this period did not alter this original asymmetry, with the EU still lacking at the dawn of the Covid-19 pandemic a fiscal capacity.

The argument of this chapter is that the measures adopted by the EU institutions and member states to address the devastating economic damages of Covid-19 have had important implications for Europe's EMU, leading towards a major rebalancing between the economic and the monetary elements of EMU. Indeed, the chapter suggests that the extraordinary measures prompted by the Covid-19 pandemic constitute a watershed in the process of European integration. In particular, besides the early emergency support measures deployed by the European Commission,³ the ECB,⁴ and the Eurogroup,⁵ the real game changer emerged with the EU recovery plan known as "Next Generation EU" (NGEU). This initiative, sponsored by several member states⁶ and proposed by the European Commission in May 2020,⁷ was approved by the European Council in July 2020,⁸ and eventually entered into force in spring 2021. NGEU consists in the creation of a new €750bn EU Recovery Fund. This is resourced by raising common debt on the financial markets; it is disbursed to the member states (between 2021 and 2026) both in the forms of grants and loans; and it will be repaid (after 2028) by raising new EU own resources. As such, by endowing the European Commission, for the first time, with significant borrowing, spending and taxing powers, NGEU

³ European Commission press release 'Coronavirus: Commission proposes to activate fiscal framework's general escape clause to respond to pandemic', 20 March 2020, IP/20/499.

⁴ Decision (EU) 2020/440 of the European Central Bank of 24 March 2020 on a temporary pandemic emergency purchase programme (ECB/2020/17), OJ 2020 L 91/1.

⁵ Council of the EU Report on the comprehensive economic policy responses to the Covid-19 pandemic, 9 April 2020.

⁶ French-German Initiative for a European Recovery from the Coronavirus Crisis, 18 May 2020.

⁷ European Commission Communication on 'Europe's Moment: Repair and Prepare for the Next Generation', 27 May 2020, COM(2020)456 final.

⁸ European Council Conclusions, 17-18-19-20-21 July 2020, EUCO 10/20.

represents a paradigm change in the functioning of EMU, pushing the EU architecture of economic governance towards an arrangement akin to that of federal regimes.

The chapter surveys the various EU legal and policy measures adopted to contain the economic effects of Covid-19, and considers their implications for the EU constitutional architecture of economic governance. In particular, the chapter outlines how by strengthening the so-far under-developed economic leg of EMU, NGEU constitutes a turning point in the process of European integration which profoundly changes the constitutional outlook of EMU, and in turn raises important questions on the future of the EU. By embracing a chronological perspective, the chapter highlights the difficulties in establishing NGEU: to this end, the chapter traces both the initial political opposition to this initiative, and the subsequent challenges to its entry into force, due to interplay between NGEU and the rule of law crisis. As the chapter underlines, in fact, NGEU risked becoming a casualty of the rule of law crisis -- with a threat by Hungary and Poland to block the entry into force of this innovative instrument in the attempt to avoid the entry into force of a regulation conditioning disbursement of EU funding to respect for the rule of law.

As such, this chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 analyses the initial EU policy measures adopted to tackle the economic damages of the Covid-19 pandemic focusing in particular on the action taken by the European Commission, the ECB and the Eurogroup. Section 3 considers instead the NGEU Recovery Fund, put forward by the Commission in May 2020 and endorsed by the European Council in July 2020, as well as its difficult entry into force in December 2020, after the European Council overcame the veto by Hungary and Poland against it. Section 4 discusses then how the pandemic-related economic policy measures adopted during Covid-19, most notably NGEU, represent a paradigm change for the EU architecture of economic governance by rebalancing the monetary and the economic legs of EMU. Section 5, finally, concludes.

II. EARLY RESPONSES TO COVID-19

The explosion of Covid-19 constituted a major challenge for the EU, and EMU specifically. While EU member states in an earlier phase of the pandemic mostly focused on containing the spread of contagions, attention rapidly shifted to the devastating socio-economic consequences of the pandemic.⁹ At the same time, while member states quickly deployed domestic measures to tackle the sudden freezing of the economy - including the postponement of tax deadlines, injection of cash to support firms and workers, and guarantees on bank loans - the nature of the crises forced EU member states to promptly coordinate action at supranational level too.

A. The Suspension of the Stability & Growth Pact

With the pandemic, and the health measures to contain it, bringing to a sudden halt the global economy, on 20 March 2020 the European Commission for the first time ever triggered the general escape clause of the Stability & Growth Pact (SGP),¹⁰ putting on hold temporarily the application of EMU fiscal rules. This assessment, which suspended the key deficit and debt rule governing member states' fiscal policy, was immediately accepted by the Council on 23 March 2020,¹¹ hence creating greater margin of manoeuvre for the member states to inject financial resources in the economy to deal with the supply and demand shocks caused by the pandemic. Also on 20 March 2020, then the Commission suspended the application of state aid rules,¹² giving greater leeway to

⁹ European Parliament Resolution of 17 April 2020 on EU coordinated action to combat the Covid-19 pandemic and its consequences, P9 TA(2020)0054.

¹⁰ European Commission press release “Coronavirus: Commission proposes to activate fiscal framework's general escape clause to respond to pandemic”, 20 March 2020, IP/20/499 .

¹¹ Council of the EU Statement, 23 March 2020.

¹² European Commission Communication on “Temporary Framework for State aid measures to support the economy in the current Covid-19 outbreak”, 20 March 2020, 2020/C 91 I/01.

member states in supporting ailing firms. At the same time, the Commission activated the EU Solidarity Fund, to provide some cash aid to member states,¹³ and also put together a coronavirus response investment initiative, which redirects up to €37bn of available cash reserves in the EU Structural and Investment Funds towards Covid-19-related expenses.¹⁴

Moreover, the European Commission also proposed the establishment of a European instrument for temporary support to mitigate unemployment risks in an emergency (SURE)¹⁵ – a secondary insurance system designed to support the heavily under-pressure national unemployment insurance regimes through loans backed-up by member states’ guarantees.¹⁶ In particular, the Commission proposal - which was based on Article 122 Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) - envisaged establishing an instrument, worth €100bn, which would provide financial assistance in the form of loans to the member states, whose public expenditures had suddenly and severely increased as of February 2020 due to the adoption of national measures directly related to short-time work schemes and similar measures to address the unemployment caused by the pandemic. From a financing point of view, the Commission proposed to establish SURE on the

¹³ Regulation (EU) 2020/461 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 March 2020 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 2012/2002 in order to provide financial assistance to Member States and to countries negotiating their accession to the Union that are seriously affected by a major public health emergency, OJ 2020 L 99/9.

¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2020/460 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 March 2020 amending Regulations (EU) No 1301/2013, (EU) No 1303/2013 and (EU) No 508/2014 as regards specific measures to mobilise investments in the healthcare systems of Member States and in other sectors of their economies in response to the COVID-19 outbreak (Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative), OJ 2020 L 99/5.

¹⁵ European Commission Proposal for a Council Regulation on the establishment of a European instrument for temporary support to mitigate unemployment risks in an emergency (SURE) following the COVID-19 outbreak, 2 April 2020, COM(2020)139 final.

¹⁶ See also C Dias, A Zoppè, ‘The SURE: Main Features’, European Parliament Research Service in-depth analysis, 28 May 2020.

basis of irrevocable guarantees by the member states, worth €25bn, which allowed the EU to contract borrowing on the financial markets in line with the EU budget constraints.

B. The Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme

Nevertheless, the most significant initial effort to support the EU member states' response to the economic consequences of Covid-19 came from EU financial institutions. While the European Investment Bank¹⁷ (EIB) developed a special Covid-19 investment scheme of €40bn to support small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), the most powerful response to the economic uncertainties caused by the Covid-19 pandemic came from the ECB. Thanks to its federal-like features, the ECB had already played a key role in responding to the euro-crisis. In fact, it was the statement by then ECB President Mario Draghi in July 2012 that the ECB would do 'whatever it takes' to save the euro¹⁸ which was perceived to be crucial in stabilizing the single currency. Moreover, to respond to the euro-crisis the ECB had deployed a number of ground-breaking unconventional monetary policies, including a Securities Market Program (SMP) in 2010 to purchase government bonds on the secondary market;¹⁹ an Outright Monetary Transaction (OMT) plan to buy state securities of countries which accepted to enter into an ESM-financed support program;²⁰ and a quantitative easing program – known as Public Sector Purchase Programme (PSPP),²¹ which significantly contributed in supporting growth policies in the EMU states.

¹⁷ European Investment Bank press release "EIB Group Will Rapidly Mobilize up to \$40 billion to Fight Crisis Caused by Covid-19", 16 March 2020.

¹⁸ ECB President Mario Draghi, speech at the Global Investment Conference, London, 26 July 2012.

¹⁹ Decision of the ECB of 14 May 2010 *establishing a securities market programme* (ECB/2010/5), OJ 2010 L124/8.

²⁰ ECB, Press release, 'Technical Features of Outright Monetary Transactions', 6 September 2012.

²¹ See Decision (EU) 2015/774 of the European Central Bank of 4 March 2015 on a secondary markets public sector asset purchase programme (ECB/2015/10), OJ 2015 L 121/20, amended several times.

The initial ECB response to Covid-19 proved once again its centrality in EMU. On 24 March 2020, in fact, the ECB launched a new Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme (PEPP),²² in which it committed to buy public bonds and commercial papers in the financial markets up to €750bn, which then subsequently almost doubled in size to €1350bn,²³ and then further increased to €1850bn.²⁴ The PEPP presented features similar to the PSPP, the quantitative easing program which the ECB had established in 2015 to fight deflation. However, it also differed from it in allowing the ECB to buy government bonds without having to adhere to the member states' capital key allocation, so as to maximize its impact in supporting those Eurozone member states most affected by the pandemic and its consequences.²⁵ PEPP greatly contributed to stabilize the financial markets, essentially securing all the necessary funding for member states, which were issuing debt to pay for the massive pandemic-related recovery measures adopted at the national level.

Nevertheless, despite the importance of the ECB action, its role was called into question as a result of legal challenges before Germany's Constitutional Court, the *Bundesverfassungsgericht* (BVerfG), which coincidentally occurred in the early phases of the Covid-19 pandemic. In fact, on 5 May 2020 the BVerfG took the unprecedented step to declare the ECB PSPP program illegal, and simultaneously declared a judgment of the European Court of Justice (ECJ) inapplicable in Germany.²⁶ Whereas already in 2014 the BVerfG has raised concerns for the ECB monetary policy,²⁷ but eventually retracted its views,²⁸ abiding by an ECJ judgment which had upheld the

²² Decision (EU) 2020/440 of the European Central Bank of 24 March 2020 on a temporary pandemic emergency purchase programme (ECB/2020/17), OJ L 91, 25.3.2020

²³ Monetary policy decisions, in European Central Bank press release of 4 June 2020.

²⁴ Monetary policy decisions, in European Central Bank press release of 10 December 2020.

²⁵ A Mooij, 'The Legality of the European Central Bank's Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme', BRIDGE Working Paper No. 5/2020.

²⁶ See BVerfG, 2 BvR 859/15, 2 BvR 980/16, 2 BvR 2006/15, 2 BvR 1651/15, judgment of 5 May 2020.

²⁷ See BVerfG 2 BvR 2728/13 et al, order of 7 February 2014.

²⁸ See BVerfG 2 BvR 2728/13 et al, judgment of 21 June 2016.

OMT program,²⁹ in its recent judgment the BVerfG crossed the Rubicon and for the first time ever declared EU action ultra vires.³⁰ In its ruling the BVerfG refused to follow the judgment of the ECJ in *Weiss*³¹ – which had already declared the PSPP as compatible with the EU treaties – and imposed a three-month time-frame on the ECB to better explain the proportionality of its program. The ruling of the BVerfG drew a strong response from the EU institutions.³² In fact, there is no doubt that the BVerfG ruling threatens the EU legal order,³³ and constitutes an illegal breach of the principle of the supremacy of EU law, which is designed to guarantee the equality of the member states in front of the treaties.³⁴ However, the judgment also posed a potential threat to further ECB action because, even though it explicitly declared that it was considering PSPP and not PEPP, it still endeavored to set limits on the ability of the ECB to pursue its mandate.

C. The Eurogroup Package

The actions of the Commission and the ECB were eventually backed up also by the intervention of the intergovernmental institutions. This was not an easy process and the European Council initially struggled to reach an agreed-upon course of action. In fact, the member states were heavily split on what new measures to put in place to sustain the economy during the pandemic and relaunch it

²⁹ See Case C-62/14 *Gauweiler*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:400.

³⁰ S Baroncelli, 'Monetary Policy and Judicial Review' in F Fabbrini, M Ventoruzzo (eds), *Research Handbook on European Economic Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019) 199.

³¹ See Case C-493/17 *Weiss*, ECLI:EU:C:2019:1046.

³² See European Commission President Ursula Von der Leyen, Statement, 10 May 2020, 20/846.

³³ See also F Fabbrini, D Kelemen, 'With One Court Decision, Germany May be Plunging Europe into a Constitutional Crisis', Op-Ed, *The Washington Post*, 7 May 2020.

³⁴ See F Fabbrini, 'After the OMT Case: The Supremacy of EU Law as the Guarantee of the Equality Between the Member States' (2015) 16 *German Law Journal* 1003.

afterwards.³⁵ In particular, on 25 March 2020 a group of nine euro area states – Belgium, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovenia, and Spain – requested in a letter to the European Council President that the EU start ‘working on a common debt instrument issued by a European institution to raise funds on the market on the same basis and to the benefit of all Member States’.³⁶ Yet Germany and the Netherlands fiercely rejected this proposal as an unacceptable effort of debt mutualisation and rather called for using the ESM as a crisis response tool.³⁷ In this context, the European Council, meeting by video-conference for three times in two weeks in March 2020, failed to reach a deal³⁸ – and pushed the file to the Eurogroup.

Eventually, on 9 April 2020 the Eurogroup, meeting in an inclusive format (open to member states from outside the Eurozone) came up with a package of measures to respond to the economic consequences of Covid-19, worth potentially €540bn.³⁹ First, the Eurogroup decided to create a pan-European guarantee fund of €25bn for the EIB, thus expanding its ability to deploy up to €200bn of financing for companies.⁴⁰ Second, the Eurogroup decided to open the possibility of using the ESM to support domestic financing of direct and indirect healthcare, cure, and prevention related costs due to the Covid-19 crisis. Specifically, in their role as members of the Governing Board of the ESM, Eurozone Ministers of Finance decided to establish a Pandemic Crisis Support Line, which would be available to all euro area member states during these times of crisis with

³⁵ See also S Grund et al, ‘Sharing the Fiscal Burden of the Crisis’, *Hertie School Jacques Delors Centre policy paper*, 7 April 2020.

³⁶ Joint letter of Belgium, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain to the European Council President Charles Michel, 25 March 2020.

³⁷ Statement from Dutch Finance Minister Wopke Hoekstra at the Tweede Kamer of 7 April 2019.

³⁸ See Joint statement of the Members of the European Council, 26 March 2020.

³⁹ Council of the EU Report, see supra 5.

⁴⁰ European Investment Bank press release ‘EIB Board Approves \$25 Billion Pan-European Guarantee Fund in Response to Covid-19 Crisis’, 26 May 2020.

standardized terms and a value of up to 2% of a member state GDP at end-of-2019 terms.⁴¹ Third, the Eurogroup also approved the Commission proposal for the establishment of SURE on the basis of Article 122 TFEU and committed €25bn national guarantees allowing the Commission to raise up to €100bn of capitals on the financial market.⁴²

Moreover, the Eurogroup also agreed to work on ‘a Recovery Fund to prepare and support the recovery, providing funding through the EU budget to programmes designed to kick-start the economy in line with European priorities and ensuring EU solidarity with the most affected member states.’⁴³ Due to divisions among member states, details on the latter were scant. Nevertheless, the gravity of the pandemic prompted in subsequent weeks a highly salient change of position by Germany, which abandoned its traditional opposition to common debt, and opened itself up toward innovative solutions to deal with Covid-19 on the understanding that the euro area financial crisis-related instruments, and especially the ESM, were not fit for this new purpose.⁴⁴ In fact, on 18 May 2020, France and Germany jointly put forward an initiative for a European Recovery Fund, proposing to establish a temporary and targeted facility connected to the new EU budget and worth €500bn, to be funded by borrowing on the markets and disbursed through grants (rather than loans) to the member states worst hit by the crisis.⁴⁵

⁴¹ G Zaccaroni, ‘The Future of the ESM within a Hybrid EMU Law’, (2020) 6 *BRIDGE Working Paper*.

⁴² Council Regulation (EU) 2020/672 of 19 May 2020 on the establishment of a European instrument for temporary support to mitigate unemployment risks in an emergency (SURE) following the Covid-19 outbreak, OJ 2020 L 159/1.

⁴³ Council of the EU Report, see supra 5, para 16

⁴⁴ German Finance Minister Olaf Scholz, ‘Interview ‘Jemand muss vorangehen’’, *Die Zeit*, 19 May 2020 www.zeit.de/zustimmung?url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.zeit.de%2F2020%2F22%2Folaf-scholz-europaeische-union-reform-vereinigte-staaten.

⁴⁵ French-German Initiative (n 6).

III. THE RECOVERY FUND NGEU

The Franco-German initiative opened the way to the European Commission, and ultimately shaped the response to Covid-19, which was embraced by the European Council. However, the entry into force of the Recovery Fund remained subject to additional unforeseen challenges - connected to the rule of law crisis rather than to the pandemic - which almost threatened the whole initiatives, and were eventually resolved only in December 2020.

A. The May 2020 European Commission proposal

On 27 May 2020, the European Commission presented an ambitious proposal for an EU recovery plan to repair the economic damages of the health crisis and to prepare the EU for the next generation. Specifically, the Commission proposed a major increase of EU resources, revamping the size of the next Multi-Annual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021-2027,⁴⁶ and creating a new €750bn recovery fund, called NGEU, connected to the MFF, and designed to support member states and businesses affected by Covid-19.⁴⁷ From a policy viewpoint, the European Commission⁴⁸ proposed that NGEU would provide resources, two-thirds of which would be disbursed as grants and one-third as loans, to fund the re-constitution of the EU economy along the Commission priorities of a green deal, digitalisation and social inclusion. Moreover, in a major break with the past, the Commission proposed that the recovery instrument would be financed by the issuance of

⁴⁶ European Commission Communication on ‘Europe’s Moment: Repair and Prepare for the Next Generation’, 27 May 2020, COM(2020)456 final.

⁴⁷ European Commission Communication “on the EU budget powering the recovery plan for Europe”, 27 May 2020 COM(2020)442 final.

⁴⁸ European Commission Proposal for a Council Regulation establishing a European Union Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic, 28 May 2020, COM(2020)441 final.

new EU debt on the financial markets (rather than states' transfers), to be repaid after 2028 and before 2058 through an increase of the headroom in the own resource ceilings,⁴⁹ and prospectively the introduction of new EU taxes.

From a legal viewpoint, the European Commission based NGEU on a multi-faceted legal constellation. On the one hand, the Commission proposed an EU Recovery Instrument (EURI),⁵⁰ to be adopted as a Council regulation based on Article 122 TFEU – which allows the adoption of measures appropriate to the economic situation in a spirit of solidarity between member states – indicating the size of NGEU and the allocation of the funds. The EURI was then complemented by a Recovery and Resilience Facility (RFF)⁵¹ – a regulation to be jointly adopted by the EP and Council, on the basis of Article 175 TFEU, on economic, social and territorial cohesion – regulating the objectives and the governance of NGEU. On the other hand, the Commission proposed to revise the EU Own Resources Decision (ORD)⁵² – the Council legal act, adopted on the basis of Article 311 TFEU, which authorizes the raising of EU revenues – increasing the EU expenditures ceilings and empowering the EU to issue debt. At the same time, the Commission connected NGEU to the MFF – the multiannual expenditure bill, to be approved by the Council ex Article 312 TFEU – as

⁴⁹ European Commission Amended Proposal for a Council Decision on the system of Own Resources of the European Union, 28 May 2020, COM(2020)445 final.

⁵⁰ European Commission Proposal for a Council Regulation establishing a European Union Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic, 28 May 2020, COM(2020)441 final.

⁵¹ European Commission Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council establishing a Recovery and Resilience Facility, 28 May 2020, COM(2020)408 final.

⁵² European Commission amended Proposal for a Council Decision on the system of Own Resources of the European Union, 28 May 2020, COM(2020)445 final.

well as to the regulation on a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the EU budget against the continuing phenomenon of rule of law backsliding.⁵³

The Commission recovery plan built on prior proposals by Spain,⁵⁴ and France and Germany⁵⁵ jointly, and tracked the strategy endorsed by the EP.⁵⁶ Nevertheless, by proposing to endow the EU with new fiscal powers, the Commission proposal was met with initial pushbacks. In fact, on 20 May 2020, a coalition of northern countries – the Netherlands, Austria, Denmark and Sweden – responded to the Franco-German initiative with a joint non-paper which instead proposed the creation of an Emergency Fund disbursing loans to states, de facto along the model of the ESM.⁵⁷ Moreover, criticism against the Recovery Fund was articulated by the Visegrád countries – Poland, Hungary, Czechia and Slovakia – which complained that the instrument did not set aside sufficient funding for lower income Member States and introduced against their wishes a rule of law conditionality in the disbursement of EU funds.⁵⁸ As a result, a first European Council meeting scheduled on 19 June 2020 to discuss the Commission proposal was unable to find an agreement,⁵⁹ prompting the organization of a new summit just a few days afterwards.⁶⁰

⁵³ European Commission Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on the protection of the Union's budget in case of generalised deficiencies as regards the rule of law in the Member States, 2 May 2018, COM(2018)324 final .

⁵⁴ Spain, Non-paper on a European recovery strategy, 19 April 2020

⁵⁵ French-German Initiative (n 6).

⁵⁶ European Parliament Resolution of 15 May 2020 on the new multiannual financial framework, own resources and the recovery plan, P9 TA(2020)0124.

⁵⁷ Austria, Denmark, the Netherlands and Sweden, Non-paper EU support for efficient and sustainable Covid-19 recovery, 20 May 2020.

⁵⁸ Czech Republic Government press release “V4 Common Lines regarding the Multiannual Financial Framework / Next Generation EU”, 11 June 2020.

⁵⁹ European Council President Charles Michel Remarks, 19 June 2020.

⁶⁰ European Council President Charles Michel Remarks, 10 July 2020.

B. The European Council July 2020 Deal

Eventually, after five days of meeting on 17-18-19-20 and 21 July 2020, the European Council managed to find a deal on the EU recovery plan, and, relatedly, on the next MFF.⁶¹ In the longest European Council since the 2001 Nice Summit, EU heads of state and government approved the new MFF for a value of €1074bn. At the same time, they approved the establishment of NGEU, worth €750bn, thus authorizing the Commission to issue debt on behalf of the EU, and envisioning a roadmap for the introduction of new taxes aimed at repaying the capital and interest of the money borrowed. To muster the necessary unanimity, the European Council amended the Commission's plan, reducing the overall size of grants from €500bn to €390bn, and increasing the loans component from €250bn to €360bn.⁶² Moreover, as requested by northern Member States, the European Council agreed to cap the size of the next MFF,⁶³ and maintain their rebates.⁶⁴ Furthermore, to obtain the crucial support of Central and Eastern Member States, it avoided any detail on the obligation to respect the rule of law as a condition to receive EU funding.⁶⁵ At the same time, the European Council somehow left unsettled the governance of the NGEU – entrusting the management to the Commission, but subject to control of the Economic and Financial Committee (EFC), and with a back-up role for itself in extraordinary cases.⁶⁶

Crucially, however, the European Council gave its blessing to the establishment of a highly innovative Recovery Fund. On the one hand, it authorized the Commission for the first time to act as a quasi-EU treasury and borrow substantive amounts of funds, totalling €750bn 'on behalf of the

⁶¹ European Council Conclusions, 17-18-19-20-21 July 2020, EUCO 10/20 cit.

⁶² *ibid* para. A6

⁶³ *ibid* para. A23

⁶⁴ *ibid* para. A30

⁶⁵ *ibid* para. A24

⁶⁶ *ibid* para. A19

Union on the capital markets'.⁶⁷ The European Council clarified that such funding was due to be used to secure the European recovery from the pandemic, as well as to strengthen the EU economic resilience. On the other hand, the EU also agreed on a roadmap to repay this common debt through new, genuine EU taxes. While the European Council agreed to increase the EU spending ceiling during the next MFF,⁶⁸ it also committed to 'work towards reforming the own resources system and introduce new own resources,'⁶⁹ with a new plastic tax,⁷⁰ a carbon border adjustment tax, a digital tax,⁷¹ and potentially a financial transaction tax.⁷²

C. The Implementation of NGEU

Some of the details in the European Council agreement were met with scepticism by the European Parliament,⁷³ which according to Article 312 TFEU has a veto right on the approval of the MFF. The European Parliament, therefore, leveraged its budgetary powers, and in subsequent negotiations with the Council of the EU, managed to secure a slight increase in the MFF, as well as to strengthen the rule of law conditionality applicable to the disbursement of EU funds, both under the MFF and the NGEU. Yet, while a political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council was achieved on such revised package deal,⁷⁴ in November 2020 Hungary and Poland put their veto to

⁶⁷ *ibid* para. A3

⁶⁸ *ibid* para. A9

⁶⁹ *ibid* para. 145

⁷⁰ *ibid* para. 146

⁷¹ *ibid* para. 147

⁷² *ibid* para. 149

⁷³ European Parliament Resolution of 23 July 2020 on the conclusions of the extraordinary European Council meeting of 17-21 July 2020 P9 TA(2020)0206.

⁷⁴ Council of the EU press release "MFF and Recovery Package: Council Presidency Reaches Political Agreement with European Parliament", 10 November 2020, PRESS 763/20.

the MFF and NGEU as a way to block the entry into force of the EU rule of law conditionality regulation.⁷⁵ As is well known, Hungary and Poland are two member states which have been experiencing in the last decade a dramatic backsliding in respect for the rule of law and democracy.⁷⁶ In fact, the EU had responded to the increasing threats to the independence of the national judiciary, freedom of the media, and respect for human rights, by activating Article 7 Treaty on EU (TEU).⁷⁷ Hungary's and Poland's action, however, threatened NGEU.⁷⁸

Nevertheless, ultimately in December 2020 member states in the European Council managed to overcome the Polish and Hungarian veto,⁷⁹ albeit in a way which diluted the impact of the rule of law regulation. In its conclusions the European Council adopted a political declaration on the rule of law conditionality regulation which dictated action for all the other EU institutions. In particular, to soothe Hungary and Poland, the European Council determined that the regulation ought to be interpreted in such a way that “the mere finding that a breach of the rule of law has taken place does not suffice to trigger the mechanism.”⁸⁰ Moreover, the European Council mandated the Commission to adopt guidelines on the application of the regulation.⁸¹ At the same time, it ruled

⁷⁵ Joint Declaration of the Prime Minister of Poland and the Prime Minister of Hungary, 26 November 2020.

⁷⁶ See inter alia B Bugarcic, ‘Central Europe’s Descent into Autocracy: A Constitutional Analysis of Authoritarian Populism’ (2019) *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 597 and R Uitz, ‘The Perils of Defending Rule of Law through Dialogue’ (2019) 15 *European Constitutional Law Review* 1.

⁷⁷ See in particular European Commission reasoned proposal in accordance with Article 7(1) Treaty on European Union for a Council Decision on the determination of a clear risk of a serious breach by the Republic of Poland of the rule of law, 20 December 2017, COM(2017) 835 final and European Parliament resolution of 12 September 2018 on a proposal calling on the Council to determine, pursuant to Article 7(1) of the Treaty on European Union, the existence of a clear risk of a serious breach by Hungary of the values on which the Union is founded, P8 TA(2018)0340.

⁷⁸ R Uitz, ‘Funding Illiberal Democracy’ (2020) 7 *BRIDGE Working Paper*.

⁷⁹ European Council Conclusions, 10-11 December 2020, EUCO 22/20

⁸⁰ *ibid* para. 2.e).

⁸¹ *ibid.* para. 2.c).

that these were to be finalized only after a forthcoming action of annulment to be brought by Hungary and Poland against the regulation.⁸² As the EP immediately pointed out in a highly critical resolution,⁸³ the European Council had clearly overstepped its powers, and “the content of [its] conclusions on the Regulation on a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the Union budget [were] superfluous.”⁸⁴ First, they did not change the text of the regulation, which had already been approved by the EP and Council. Secondly, “any political declaration of the European Council cannot be deemed to represent an interpretation of legislation as interpretation is vested within the [ECJ].”⁸⁵ Thirdly, “the conclusions of the European Council cannot be made binding on the Commission in applying legal acts.”⁸⁶

Albeit at a high moral price, the European Council compromise led to the formal legal approval, just in time before the end of 2020, of the ORD,⁸⁷ the new MFF 2021-27,⁸⁸ and the EURI.⁸⁹ This was accompanied also by the rule of law conditionality regulation,⁹⁰ and an inter-

⁸² *ibid.* See now also Case C-156/21 *Hungary v. European Parliament and Council* ECLI:EU:C:2022:97 and Case C-157/21 *Poland v. European Parliament and Council* ECLI:EU:C:2022:98.

⁸³ See European Parliament resolution of 17 December 2020 on the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027, the Inter-Institutional Agreement, the EU Recovery Instrument and the Rule of Law Regulation, P9 TA(2020)0360.

⁸⁴ *ibid.*, para. 4.

⁸⁵ *ibid.*, para. 5.

⁸⁶ *ibid.*, para. 8.

⁸⁷ Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053 of 14 December 2020 on the system of own resources of the European Union, OJ 2020 L 424/1.

⁸⁸ Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2093 of 17 December 2020 laying down the multiannual financial framework for the years 2021 to 2027, OJ 2020 L 433I/11.

⁸⁹ Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 of 14 December 2020 establishing a European Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the COVID-19 crisis OJ 2020 L 433I/23

⁹⁰ Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2092 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the Union budget, OJ 2020 L 433I/1.

institutional agreement on a road-map to introduce new taxes,⁹¹ and later followed by the RFF in February 2021.⁹² In Spring 2021, therefore, EU member states were asked to approve the ORD, as required by Article 311(3) TFEU, as this conditioned the financing of the MFF and the issuance of EU bonds under NGEU. During the ratification process, NGEU was thus put on hold for almost a month in April 2021, when the BverfG temporarily suspended Germany's ratification of the ORD,⁹³ until it rejected in preliminary terms the constitutional challenge raised against NGEU by anti-EU applicants.⁹⁴ Therefore, since the end of May 2021, following the approval by all national parliaments of the ORD,⁹⁵ the EU has been endowed with a powerful Recovery Fund, supporting member states to rebuild their economies and social structures ravaged by the Covid-19 pandemic. In particular, in June 2021 the European Commission has started issuing bonds on the financial

⁹¹ Interinstitutional Agreement between the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission on budgetary discipline, on cooperation in budgetary matters and on sound financial management, as well as on new own resources, including a roadmap towards the introduction of new own resources Interinstitutional Agreement of 16 December 2020 between the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission on budgetary discipline, on cooperation in budgetary matters and on sound financial management, as well as on new own resources, including a roadmap towards the introduction of new own resources, OJ 2020 L 433I/28.

⁹² Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility, OJ 2021 L 57/17.

⁹³ See 2 BvR 547/ 21, order of 26 March 2021.

⁹⁴ See and 2 BvR 547/ 21, order of 15 April 2021.

⁹⁵ See also A D'Alessandro, 'National Ratification of the Own Resources Decision', European Parliament Research Service Briefing, June 2021.

markets,⁹⁶ and since July 2022 it has began pre-financing the national recovery and resilience plans that member states have presented to receive NGEU funds.⁹⁷

IV. THE IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESPONSES TO COVID-19 FOR EMU

The multiplicity of legal and institutional measures adopted to address the economic consequences of Covid-19 profoundly affected the architecture of EU economic governance. In fact, as a result of the pandemic-response initiatives, the constitutional outlook of EMU has significantly changed, with the EU now enjoying fiscal powers that were, until recently, seen as impossible to achieve.⁹⁸ According to some, this is a dividend of Brexit, as the UK withdrawal from the EU removed a veto player who would most certainly have opposed such a dramatic transfer of borrowing, spending and taxing power from the national to the supranational level.⁹⁹ Be that as it may, the EU responses to Covid-19 proved the resilience of the European project, and significantly differed from the responses to the euro-crisis. NGEU, in particular, rebalanced the economic (E) and monetary (M) legs of EMU, and effectively endowed the EU with the fiscal capacity which it hitherto lacked.

⁹⁶ See European Commission press release, ‘NextGenerationEU: European Commission raises €20 billion in first transaction to support Europe’s recovery’, 15 June 2021, IP/21/2982.

⁹⁷ See e.g. European Commission press release, ‘NextGenerationEU: European Commission endorses Italy’s €19,5 billion recovery and resilience plan’, 22 June 2021, IP/21/3126.

⁹⁸ European Commissioner Thierry Breton, ‘La fin de la naïveté’, *Les Echos*, 10 August 2020, <https://www.lesechos.fr/idees-debats/cercle/la-fin-de-la-naivete-1229485>.

⁹⁹ See ‘The EU’s recovery fund is a benefit of Brexit’, *The Economist*, 30 May 2020.

A. The Responses to the Covid-19 Crisis Compared to the Euro-crisis

The developments occurred in EMU in response to Covid-19 go well beyond what occurred in response to the euro crisis. While there is still extensive debate among political scientists whether the legal and institutional measures adopted to tackle the euro area financial crisis strengthened more the EU intergovernmental institutions¹⁰⁰ or rather the EU supranational ones,¹⁰¹ there is little doubt that in legal terms the new powers acquired by the European Commission were purely coordinating powers, as evident in the framework of the European Semester. Instead, departing from a ‘surveillance model’ of fiscal federalism,¹⁰² NGEU shifts to the EU a significant degree of new, *real* fiscal powers – including the ability for the Commission to raise and mobilize resources, and run a supranational economic policy, investing in transnational political priorities like the Green Deal, and digitalisation.¹⁰³

In fact, thanks to NGEU the EU now presents features which are similar to those of mature federal systems, all of which are endowed with a centralized counter-cyclical fiscal tool to support the economic policy of component units, also via grants.¹⁰⁴ From a legal point of view, this EMU development occurred without an amendment of the EU treaties. The existing legal bases -- including Article 122 TFEU (on financial solidarity) jointly with Articles 311 and 312 TFEU (the provisions on the ORD and the MFF), as well as Article 175 TFEU (on social and territorial

¹⁰⁰ U Puetter, *The European Council and the Council: New Intergovernmentalism and Institutional Change* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2014).

¹⁰¹ J D Savage, A Verdun, ‘Strengthening the European Commission’s budgetary and economic surveillance capacity since Greece and the euro area crisis: a study of five Directorates’ (2016) *Journal of European Public Policy* 101.

¹⁰² A Hinarejos, ‘Fiscal Federalism in the European Union’ (2013) *Common Market Law Review* 1621.

¹⁰³ B de Witte, ‘The European Union’s Covid-19 Recovery Plan: The Legal Engineering of an Economic Policy Shift’ (2021) 58 *Common Market Law Review* 635

¹⁰⁴ S Yilmaz, F Zahir (eds), *Intergovernmental Transfers in Federations* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing 2020).

cohesion) -- provided a constitutional grounding to increase the EU fiscal power to tackle Covid-19. Interestingly, this resembles the expansion of federal fiscal powers in the United States (US), which occurred during the New Deal in the 1930s without any formal amendment of the US Constitution.¹⁰⁵ Nevertheless, the constitutional significance of these changes for the architecture of European economic governance did not go unnoticed at the national level. In fact, challenges to the legality of NGEU have been raised, e.g., in Germany and Finland, notably in the context of the domestic ratification of the ORD. These challenges have so far proved unsuccessful, confirming that the EU treaties can dynamically adapt in light of changing circumstances.¹⁰⁶ But they reveal the paradigm change brought about by NGEU, compared to the euro-crisis.

How can we explain the difference in the responses to the euro-crisis and the pandemic? Several explanations can be put forward. First, the euro-crisis had had asymmetrical effects, hitting differently the Northern European economies as opposed to the Southern European ones. On the contrary, the pandemic hit indiscriminately all EU member states -- even though the health measures adopted by countries were not identical, and the socio-economic costs of the pandemic varied from one country to the other. Second, the euro-crisis was blamed on the irresponsible behavior of several EU member states -- namely the spendthrift countries of the South. On the contrary, no member state could be blamed of causing the pandemic, which was an exogenous shock, entirely outside the control of any public authority. Otherwise, the risks that the economic consequences of the pandemic -- deepening the legacy of the euro-crisis -- would cause an unbridgeable economic divergence in the Eurozone, leading potentially to its disintegration, pushed particularly Germany to change its stance, and open the door towards greater financial solidarity. Finally, the humanitarian drama caused by Covid-19 - with shocking images of piles of graves in Bergamo, Italy - mobilized public opinion also in the fiscally rigorous Northern European states,

¹⁰⁵ D Super, 'Rethinking Fiscal Federalism' (2005) *Harvard Law Review* 2546.

¹⁰⁶ J-C Piris, 'Why the German Constitutional Court will (Probably) Not Kill the €750bn Recovery Fund', *European Policy Centre comment*, 7 April 2021.

convincing them on the need to develop new instruments of mutual aid to face the pandemic. And thanks to that in 2020 the EU managed to make a major leap forward with the institution of NGEU.

B. The Rebalancing of EMU

From this point of view, therefore, NGEU constitutes a paradigm change for EMU, and goes a long way towards re-balancing its original asymmetry. Through NGEU, in fact, the European Commission has acquired borrowing, spending and taxing powers that it hitherto lacked. This contributes to strengthen the economic policy leg of EMU, by making the Commission a quasi-EU Treasury office.¹⁰⁷ Certainly, the whole approval process of NGEU confirmed the intergovernmental drift at play in the EU, and the leading role of the European Council as the supreme decision-making institution. At the same time, NGEU maintains important intergovernmental features which are visible in the need to have the approval by of the ORD by each member state in accordance with its national constitutional requirement, as foreseen in Article 311 TFEU. Nevertheless, NGEU contributes in important ways to empowering the Commission with economic policy powers. Moreover, by strengthening the EU political branches, NGEU improves the collaboration between the EU monetary and fiscal institutions. Admittedly, the ECB had previously acted in concert with the EU intergovernmental institutions: for instance, the launch of OMT in 2012, followed approval of the banking union by the European Council. Nevertheless, the ECB had lamented the lack of a treasury office at the EU level.¹⁰⁸ As such, the reforms brought about in response to Covid-19 go a long way towards meeting the calls made during the last decade to complete EMU.

¹⁰⁷ European Commission Communication on ‘A European Minister of Economy and Finance’, 6 December 2017, COM(2017)823 final.

¹⁰⁸ M Chang, ‘The (Ever) Incomplete Story of Economic and Monetary Union’ (2016) *Journal of Contemporary European Research* 486.

C. The Establishment of a Fiscal Capacity

The NGEU endows the EU with a fiscal capacity -- a budgetary instrument, funded by genuine own resources, to support its spending programs. As I explained elsewhere, EU lacked a fiscal capacity even after the euro-crisis.¹⁰⁹ In fact, despite multiple proposals -- including by High Level Groups, the European Commission, the European Parliament and several member states jointly - the political cleavage between Northern and Southern EU member states which emerged during the euro-crisis had made progress on this issue impossible. Certainly the EU had the MFF. However, the general EU budget did not include much discretionary spending, as its funding is mostly pre-committed for key policy programs, including agriculture and cohesion. Moreover, notwithstanding the spirit and the letter of the EU Treaties, which require the EU budget to be funded by the EU's own resources, the MFF is for the most part today financed by contributions from the member states.¹¹⁰ As a result, EU countries consider the contributions they make to the EU budget as *their* money, and aggressively measure the difference between their contributions to, and their receipts from, the EU budget. This created an embarrassing spectacle, visible at all new MFF negotiations, revealing the unsustainability of a system where member states quarrel about how much they pay into, and get from, the EU budget.¹¹¹ From this standpoint, therefore, NGEU constitutes a game-changer: by allowing the EU to run a large budget, funded by resources raised on the capital markets and to be paid long-term by raising new EU taxes, NGEU effectively endows the EU with a

¹⁰⁹ F Fabbrini, 'A Fiscal Capacity for the Eurozone', report commissioned by the European Parliament Constitutional Affairs Committee, February 2019.

¹¹⁰ U Villani-Lubelli and L Zamparini (eds), *Features and Challenges of the EU Budget* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing 2019).

¹¹¹ M Maduro, 'A New Governance for the European Union and the Euro', study commissioned by the European Parliament Constitutional Affairs Committee, September 2012.

fiscal capacity independent from state transfers, and suitable to invest on EU programs to promote EU public goods, akin to those of federal regimes.¹¹²

Nevertheless, it remains to be seen whether NGEU constitutes a ‘Hamiltonian moment’, permanently transforming European integration, or rather an exceptional initiative to be discontinued as the pandemic abates.¹¹³ In fact, the extraordinary measures deployed by the EU institutions and the member states to tackle the Covid-19 emergency are mostly crafted as temporary responses, which raises the question whether it is conceivable after the pandemic to return to a pre-Covid-19 normal. The suspension of EU state aid rules and the SGP are meant to be provisional, with the aim to gradually re-introduce the application of these rules as soon as the health situation improves.¹¹⁴ Moreover, the SURE unemployment insurance scheme has a sunset clause, which foresees that the availability of the instrument shall end on 31 December 2022¹¹⁵ – even though the Council, on a proposal of the Commission, may decide to extend the instrument’s operation for a period of six months at a time. Most crucially, NGEU is conceived as an exceptional, one-off initiative. As the July 2020 European Council conclusions state, ‘the powers granted to the Commission to borrow are clearly limited in size, duration and scope’¹¹⁶ – a point restated in the EURI Regulation, which is defined as ‘an exceptional response to temporary but extreme circumstances.’¹¹⁷

¹¹² See also B Gordon, *The Constitutional Boundaries of European Fiscal Federalism* (Cambridge, CUP 2022).

¹¹³ S Disegni (ed), *Europe at a Crossroads after the Shock* (Milan - Monographs of RESET with Fondazione Corriere della Sera 2020).

¹¹⁴ European Commissioner Valdis Dombrovskis, ‘Dombrovskis: ‘Le regole europee di bilancio? Dopo la recessione torneranno. Il Mes è come chiesto dall’Italia’, *Corriere della Sera*, 4 July 2020, https://www.corriere.it/economia/finanza/20_luglio_04/dombrovskis-le-regole-europee-bilancio-la-recessione-torneranno-mes-come-chiesto-dall-itali-b93236fa-bd61-11ea-9366-e0fed13f309c.shtml.

¹¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2020/672 cit., Art 12(3).

¹¹⁶ European Council Conclusions 17-18-19-20-21 July 2020 EUCO 10/20 cit., para. A4.

¹¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 cit., recital 6.

Certainly, by the EU institutions' and member states' own admission, the return to normal in EMU rules and governance will not occur before a number of years have passed. In fact, with continuing uncertainty on when the pandemic will be fully contained, and new challenges on the horizon due to the Russian war of invasion of Ukraine, it cannot be excluded that the emergency measures adopted to tackle the socio-economic consequences of COVID-19 will need to be continued, or even expanded, in the time ahead. Nevertheless, there will be important pressures to time-limit the experience of NGEU, including from specific national parliaments or courts. The April 2021 decision by the BVerfG on a legal challenge brought against the German act ratifying the ORD demonstrates this.¹¹⁸ In this case, the BVerfG rejected the request for an injunction and ruled that, while proceedings on the merit of the case would continue, Germany could ratify the ORD, and thus authorize NGEU. At the same time, however, the BVerfG underlined that NGEU funds can be used exclusively to address the Covid-19 crisis and that this initiative is time-limited, and as such cannot lead to the creation of a permanent instrument.

Yet, because the adoption of NGEU constitutes a crisis-driven paradigm change for EMU, it may leave a legacy in EMU - particularly if it turns out to be a successful economic policy measure.¹¹⁹ In fact, political scientists have emphasized that institutions generally follow a logic of path-dependency, in that once an economic process or a governance arrangement is in place over time, it becomes locked-in and it will be difficult to change it, as institutional actors become accustomed to the status quo.¹²⁰ At the same time, legal scholars have also pointed out that measures adopted in times of emergency tend to sediment and become normalized as the emergency

¹¹⁸ BVerfG, 1 BvR 547/21, order of 15 April 2021.

¹¹⁹ European Commissioner Paolo Gentiloni Speech of at the Conference 'Progettiamo il Rilancio', 13 June 2020.

¹²⁰ K Dopfer, 'Toward a Theory of Economic Institutions: Synergies and Path Dependency' (1991) 25 *Journal of Economic Issues* 535.

ends.¹²¹ From this viewpoint, therefore, one cannot exclude that the policy measures put in place in response to Covid-19 will become a part of the new normal for the EU, even after Covid-19. Otherwise, it should be borne in mind that several of the measures deployed to address Covid-19 reflected policy proposals that had long been sought for by several institutional actors. For instance, SURE tracks earlier proposals for a permanent EU unemployment insurance system¹²² – and as such, its success in the Covid-19 context may pave the way for its institutionalization on a broader scale. In fact, the literature on fiscal federalism shows that when the central level of government in multi-level systems acquires new fiscal competences and the ability to mobilize resources, this tends to remain a lasting feature of the system – a pattern particularly visible in the US after the New Deal.¹²³

V. CONCLUSION

Covid-19 represented a watershed moment – not just for the life of millions of Europeans, but also for the life of the EU itself. In response to a dramatic health crisis, and with the aim to contain its devastating socio-economic consequences, the EU institutions and member states have taken unprecedented steps in 2020, with important implications for European integration in the field of economic governance. In fact, while Covid-19 has had significant negative effects on several other areas of European integration, such as Schengen and free movement, action taken to respond to the socio-economic effects of the pandemic have boosted integration in EMU. In particular, besides the initial legal and policy measures adopted by the ECB, Commission and Eurogroup, the approval of

¹²¹ F Ní Aoláin, O Gross, *Law in Times of Crises: Emergency Powers in Theory and Practice* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2006).

¹²² European Commission Roadmap for a European Unemployment Benefit Scheme, 27 January 2017.

¹²³ R Henning, M Kessler, 'Fiscal Federalism: US History for Architects of Europe's Fiscal Union', *Bruegel paper* 2012.

NGEU constitutes a paradigm change for the EU architecture of economic governance, completing EMU and rebalancing the monetary and economic pillars of EU fiscal integration in ways which are reminiscent of federal regimes.

EMU had been originally established by the Maastricht Treaty as an asymmetric regime, with a full centralization of monetary policy but without an equivalent federalization of economic policy. Even though the responses to the euro area financial crisis had prompted a number of important transformations, EMU remained incomplete. Since the explosion of the Covid-19 pandemic, however, the EU institutions and the member states have adopted a multiplicity of measures, pushing integration in fiscal affairs beyond what could ever be imagined before. In particular, the NGEU has been a game-changer. This innovative instrument empowers the Commission to borrow money on the financial markets and to transfer these resources to the member states both as grants and loans to support an inclusive recovery and the re-alignment of the EU economies towards shared EU priorities.

As this chapter has argued from an EU law and policy perspective, the transformations brought about in the architecture of EU economic governance during Covid-19 constitute a paradigm change for EMU, significantly altering its constitutional outlook. However, important questions remain about the future of NGEU, including the opportunities and obstacles to make it a permanent feature of EMU after Covid-19. In fact, while most pandemic-related measures are designed to be temporary, political science theories of historical institutionalism and legal theories of emergency legislation suggest that it is uncertain whether it would be feasible for the EU to return to a pre-Covid-19 normal, or rather whether this is the new normal for the EU. These changes have gone a long way to addressing some of EMU's ongoing weaknesses – namely the absence of a fiscal capacity. With NGEU, the EU has now been endowed with proper fiscal powers which match its monetary powers, thus rebalancing the relation between the 'economic' and 'monetary' legs of EMU. Nevertheless, such changes also require constitutional adjustments to enhance the EU's

legitimacy and effectiveness, and it remains to be seen whether they can be rolled back, or if they will consolidate as the new normal for the EMU.